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THE IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotatsiya. The article talks about important aspects of the use of information and communication technologies in the process of teaching English and the program of the preschool education system.

Kalit so'zlar: information and communication technologies, preschool education system, electronic board, computer, laptop, TV

Preschool education is the first stage of training and education of our youth. The right preschool program helps our children grow and learn according to their unique intelligence (1). That is why these primary educational institutions form the basis for subjects that play a key role in the development of mankind. The sisters of the kindergarten teach the children of this type of educational institution to count numbers, teach the mathematics of our country, and at the same time memorize various wonderful and interesting poems. As you can see, this basic knowledge allows them to quickly and easily understand the next steps. In terms of different poems, a number of poems help students broaden their worldview and enrich the world of imagination. Because the ability to imagine is the ability to draw conclusions from some acquired knowledge. Many holders of unique knowledge emphasize that it is better to expand and develop people's imagination than to deepen their knowledge. Because through imagination, humanity has made intelligent discoveries that are now familiar to us. Increasing children's ability to imagine from a young age will motivate their further learning process to be fast and efficient. In addition, by memorizing poetry, they sharpen their memory. By copying various phrases and words from these poems into their own language, they become eloquent and are able to express their opinions everywhere. A number of the processes listed above that contribute to the de-

velopment of children's science undoubtedly help our country to educate independently thinking individuals.

In the last 10-15 years, in addition to counting and memorizing various poems, the curriculum of preschool educational institutions has included teaching English. The importance of this language can be explained by the fact that 90% of the world's literature is written in English (2). But the question you might be asking is: Why is it important to teach young children another language from an early age? , or is it necessary to teach children another language other than learning to write and even read in their native language? and so on . However, Duyi scientists said that learning foreign languages is easier for children under ten years of age. During this period, the child learns the language not by understanding but mechanically, so the use and pronunciation of a foreign language is easy (2) they learn in a series of contents, like educational kings. This allows them to expand their vocabulary and improve their pronunciation. Thanks to this, their vocabulary is partially formed, and when they move to 1st grade, they will not encounter certain difficulties. Because by memorizing and telling different English words in kindergarten, the process of adaptation to this language will be formed, and when they go to school, this language will be familiar to them and easy to learn.

As we all know, it is not compulsory to attend preschool in our country. Students

studying in these institutions have a certain understanding of the English language, but the question may also arise as to what will happen to children who do not study in such educational institutions. There is no reason to think about it, because there are TV channels for children in our country. On these television channels, children are shown various cartoons in English. Through this way, they will also have some knowledge in English. The words television and television may bring information and communication technologies to your mind. Today, information and communication technologies have their place in every aspect of our life. It has had a sufficient effect on the education system. Through the use of these structures, the quality of education has become effective. As for the use of information and communication technologies in the preschool education system, the rapid development of the information society in the preschool education organization can significantly increase children's interest in learning (3). For example, by using an electronic board or a computer, they bring pictures of their new words, and they begin to speak by themselves freely, looking at this pace. In this process, the students who have difficulty learning words will quickly learn new words and can be repeated by showing pictures in this way in each lesson.

Because repetition is the mother of knowledge. When we all look at something we haven't seen before, it grabs our attention and we can't pay attention to anything

else. Children are not unfamiliar with such activities, because they are very interested in modern technologies, and they always come across such technologies in everyone's hands, at home, but because they are young, they are not given the opportunity to use them. That's why they pay attention to it when using various electronic boards, computers, laptops, and at the same time, they acquire more than 50% of knowledge by hearing and seeing, that is, new words. In conclusion, it can be said that in the process of teaching English to preschoolers with the help of information and communication technologies, they see the images of words and pay attention to the tools that seem interesting to them, and words they will have the opportunity to express themselves freely and enjoy the process

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